

Machine learning classification of infectious disease distribution status

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ABSTRACT

Infectious diseases are common diseases and are caused by microorganisms such as viruses, bacteria, and parasites. Indicators of the spread of this disease can be seen based on the population level and the number of confirmed cases. This study aims to develop a machine learning (ML) analysis model using the K-means cluster, artificial neural network (ANN), and decision tree (DT) methods. The dataset used in this study was obtained based on the number of confirmed patients and the distribution of the population. The analysis process is divided into two stages, namely preprocessing and the classification process. The pre-processing stage aims to produce a classification pattern that can describe the level of distribution status. The classification pattern will be continued at the classification analysis stage using ANN and DT. Classification analysis gave significant results with an accuracy rate of 99.77%. The results of the classification analysis can also describe the level of knowledge distribution based on the decision tree. Overall, the contribution of this research is to develop a classification analysis model that presents the latest information and knowledge. The results of the research presented also have an impact on the control process in environmental management and public health.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Analysis of the status of the spread of infectious diseases is used as a tool for the public health management process [1]. In general, these infectious diseases consist of influenza, hypertension, diarrhea, tuberculosis and others [2]. Infectious diseases cause pain, paralysis, and even death with a fairly high percentage rate of 69.91% [3]. The transmission rate is spread nationally so that it is one of the main health problems today [4]. To help solve these problems, the classification analysis process can play an active role in developing a model to provide the best alternative solution.

Classification analysis has been developed in various problems to provide the desired results [5]. These various models use several methods in conducting classification analysis [6]. The analysis model can be seen in the concept of machine learning (ML). The model has been able to contribute quite effectively to the classification process [7]. ML works optimally to present output with a fairly good level of accuracy [8]. The development of ML in several studies shows a significant graph in solving problems in the world of health [9]. These problems can be seen from the process of identification, classification, and prediction [10], [11]. In this

case, ML will also be used to carry out a classification analysis process on the problem of the status of the spread of infectious diseases.

The method that will be used in the classification analysis process involves K-means clusters, artificial neural networks (ANN), and decision trees (DT). This method can work more effectively in presenting the desired results. K-means cluster is a method that can categorize data based on mathematical calculations [12]. K-means is a very popular method used in the big data concept [13], [14]. This method works on pre-processing to produce a classification pattern [15]. The pattern obtained can be proven to be effective in carrying out the classification analysis process [16]. The results given from pre-processing using K-means clusters will be forwarded to the analysis using the ANN concept.

ANN is a concept that is widely used in ML [17]. This method is a supervised learning concept that can produce fairly good accuracy results [18]. ANN performs an analysis based on the weighted value obtained to produce the output [19]. This concept continues to develop as many problems have been well resolved [20]. In the process of analyzing the classification of the spread of infectious diseases, ANN is expected to provide optimal performance. To get these results, the stages of the training and testing process in learning will be maximized to produce outputs [21]. ANN performance can be seen based on the level of accuracy and error in the output presentation [22]. The outputs obtained in the process will later be re-analyzed in order to present the information and knowledge needed. The ANN output results obtained will be re-analyzed using the DT concept.

In general, DT works by conducting analysis based on previously obtained patterns to present knowledge-based [23]. The DT analysis process will refine the analysis of the spread of infectious diseases in the form of a decision tree. The results represented in the DT represent a previously hidden information and knowledge [24]. Several analytical models have been developed with DT such as the classification process for a disease that aims to support a decision [25].

Overall, this study presents the novelty of the classification analysis model. The model was developed through pre-processing and classification processes on the ML concept. The up-to-date model also provides a structured and systematic analysis process to provide precise and accurate output. With this, this research can to present new knowledge and information that describes the spread of infectious diseases. Furthermore, that this research will also be useful for related parties in environmental and community health management.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The classification analysis process using the machine learning concept has 2 stages, namely the pre-processing stage and the classification analysis stage. The methods and algorithms used consist of the K-means cluster, ANN, and DT. The description of the research, stages can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research stages

Figure 1 explain the analysis process starting with data analysis based on population size and infectious disease. the classification stage starts from pre-processing using the K-means cluster algorithm aimed at obtaining patterns in classification analysis. With the analysis pattern obtained, the classification process will be carried out using an ANN. ANN learning using a feedforward algorithm aims to get the maximum classification results. The classification analysis stage will be continued by using the DT method to obtain information and knowledge. The results of the analysis based on numbers present the output in the form of a DT in the status of the spread of the disease seen from the population and the number of infection cases.

2.1. Data collection

The discussion of this study uses population data and infectious disease figures for 3 periods, 2018, 2019, and 2020. The source of the data used comes from the Pesisir Selatan District Health Office. The data will be analyzed previously to be used as variables in conducting classification analysis. The variables used will be seen based on 2 indicators based on population and the number of cases of infectious diseases. The variables used in the analysis process can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Variable of classification analysis of infectious disease distribution status

Population	Variable	Infected number	Variable
Population number	X1	Ispa	X8
Male	X2	Influenza	X9
Famele	X3	Gastritis	X10
(1-12 Year)	X4	Hipertensi	X11
(1-30 Year)	X5	Diarrhea	X12
(31-45 Year)	X6	Rheumatism	X13
> 45 Year	X7	Fever	X14
		Commond cold	X15
		Asthma	X16
		Dengue fever	X17
		Tuberculosis	X18
		Dispepsia	X19
		Skin Allergies	X20

K-means cluster is an initialization algorithm for grouping data [26]. The implementation of K-means clusters can provide results in the form of analysis patterns for recommendations for classification, determination, and prediction processes [27]. K-means works by looking for and finding similar patterns in the data with the output of information and knowledge [28]. This algorithm is an exploratory analysis concept that can be applied in supervised machine learning [29]. The concept of the K-means cluster algorithm can be seen in (1) [30].

$$\sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{xi \in} ||Xi - \mu||_2^2 \tag{1}$$

2.2. Artificial neural network (ANN)

ANN is a method that is widely used in machine learning [31]. The ANN method in machine learning gives promising results to produce a comprehensive review [32]. The implementation of this concept can carry out learning in the classification analysis process with better output [33]. ANN is a non-linear concept with mathematical calculations on a modeled problem to produce the output [34]. ANN performance results provide a fairly high level of sensitivity based on network output [35].

2.3. Decision tree (DT)

DT is a classification analysis concept developed to provide decisions based on data filters [36]. The development of this method is used in the classification process by validating the tests carried out [37]. DT is used in solving problems on complex data to produce information and knowledge that is presented in the form of a DT [38]. The performance process still uses mathematical calculations in the development of decision-making systems [39]. The equations in the DT method can be seen in (2) [40].

$$Entropy(S) = - \sum_{i=1}^c PS(ci) \log PS(ci) \tag{2}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Pre-processing analysis

The pre-processing analysis stage aims to maximize the classification process that will be carried out [41]. This process can provide a better and structured analysis presentation to get better output results [42]. In this pre-processing analysis, the algorithm used is the K-means cluster. This algorithm can group data based on the level of closeness of the relationship in the data [43]. The results of the pre-processing analysis using K-means clusters can be seen in Table 2. Table 2 shows that the results of the cluster provide a classification pattern based on the group of data on the status of the spread of infectious disease numbers. The cluster results show the level of distribution with high status (C1) as many as 8 items, moderate as many as 2 items, and low as 5 items. From Table 1, it can be seen that there are 3 categories of infectious disease distribution status, namely high, medium and low status. With the results of the pre-processing, a classification process will be carried out for the spread of infectious disease numbers.

Table 2. Results of pre-processing K-means cluster

	Population (X1-X7)							Infected Number (X8-X20)										Y		
150	788	720	332	252	209	564	21	14	15	16	46	56	20	96	26	9	3	0	71	High
215	109	105	473	351	306	805	26	75	48	87	57	12	16	34	67	8	4	0	56	High
137	684	694	303	219	201	516	32	15	86	71	10	29	89	35	74	6	9	0	28	High
151	758	757	333	242	219	567	32	65	16	92	55	15	0	10	67	0	0	0	0	High
264	134	130	582	430	378	991	52	22	37	29	0	31	54	24	46	4	4	0	18	High
160	807	794	352	258	230	599	71	73	14	16	0	68	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	High
451	225	225	994	722	655	169	30	13	11	11	52	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Low
303	147	155	666	471	451	113	73	0	26	28	73	25	45	49	88	3	8	3	29	High
525	257	268	115	823	779	196	80	34	69	54	86	63	38	0	13	5	5	0	25	Midd
505	252	253	111	806	734	188	86	0	41	23	10	36	22	0	98	4	6	0	17	Midd
314	154	160	692	495	464	117	57	31	56	41	0	30	0	91	0	0	0	0	11	Low
465	230	234	102	736	680	173	36	23	28	19	38	11	18	0	24	0	0	0	0	Low
367	176	190	809	565	553	137	40	69	26	14	87	31	21	75	81	6	5	1	72	Low
727	347	380	160	111	110	272	27	0	12	72	56	56	34	87	87	6	1	0	12	High
485	240	244	106	770	709	181	29	56	18	16	79	16	24	47	68	0	0	0	13	Low

3.2. Classification analysis

The classification process in the discussion aims to see the status of the spread of infectious diseases based on infection numbers and population. In this case, the analysis process begins by using the ANN method with a feedforward algorithm. The ANN method is a concept that can carry out learning with better outputs [44]. ANN can also be implemented in the case of the classification of a disease by using the concept of feedforward learning. The results given have a fairly high level of accuracy [45]. Basically, this method learns the pattern of network architecture formed by the training and testing process [46]. The study aims to obtain the best network architecture pattern that will be used in the classification analysis process [47]. The results of the best classification of the ANN network architecture pattern can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2 is the result of the best classification ANN network architecture through the learning process by training and testing the previous classification pattern. The ANN architectural pattern has 3 layers, namely the input layer, the hidden layer, and the output layer [48]. The architecture is shown in Figure. 2 consists of a layer of 20 units of the input layer, 5 layers of hidden layers of five units namely (50, 35, 25, 15, and 10), and 1 layer of the output layer of one unit. This architectural pattern will be used to carry out the classification process on the status of the spread of infectious diseases. The results of the classification process using ANN can be seen in the learning output graph in Figure 3.

Figure 3 describes the results of the classification analysis using ANN which has a fairly good output. These results can be seen from the performance value of 0.0731% so that the ANN learning process approaches the maximum results in the classification process. ANN output can also be proven the level of relationship based on the linearity value of the input used [49]. In this case, the level of relationship between input and output units is 96.98%. These results are sufficient to illustrate that ANN is able to perform classification analysis on the status of the spread of infectious diseases.

The analysis process will still be continued with the aim of exploring knowledge based on the classification pattern that has been analyzed with ANN. The DT method can present output in the form of knowledge-based [50]. In concept, DT performs analysis to find information and knowledge hidden in a pile of data [51]. The classification analysis process using the DT concept will focus on two directions, namely based on the population level and the number of distribution figures. The purpose of this two-way classification analysis is to find information and knowledge from a different perspective. The results of the

analysis provided by DT can be used as a reference to follow up the handling process for related parties. The results of the DT classification analysis based on the population level can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4 explains that DT is capable of generating information and knowledge in the form of a DT image. The classification results presented can be seen that the population with the age category >45 years has the highest risk for transmission. then for the population aged 31-45 and under 30 years, it also has a relatively moderate level of probability. To ensure the results obtained in Figure 4, the analysis process will also be seen based on the rate of spread of infectious diseases. The results of the analysis can be described in Figures 5 and 6.

Figure 5 is the result of a DT that describes information and knowledge about the status of the spread of infectious diseases. These results are based on indicators that have been analyzed previously. Figure 6 is a form of classification rule that presents knowledge in the spread of infectious diseases. Overall the results of the classification analysis developed in the new model are able to provide significant results.

Figure 2. Architecture of ANN classification

Figure 3. Graph of learning outcomes

Figure 4. Results of DT classification analysis based on population level

Figure 5. Decision tree of classification analysis results

Tree

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Diarrhea = Low
| Asthma = Low
| | Gastritis = High: Middle {Middle=1, High=0, Low=0}
| | Gastritis = Low: Low {Middle=0, High=0, Low=3}
| | Gastritis = Middle
| | | Common Cold = Low
| | | | Hipertensi = Low: Low {Middle=0, High=0, Low=1}
| | | | Hipertensi = Middle
| | | | ISPA = High: Low {Middle=0, High=0, Low=1}
| | | | ISPA = Low: Middle {Middle=1, High=0, Low=0}
| | | | ISPA = Middle
| | | | Rheumatism = Low: Low {Middle=0, High=0, Low=2}
| | | | Rheumatism = Middle
| | | | Influenza = Low
| | | | | Skin Allergies = Low
| | | | | Fever = Middle
| | | | | Dengue Fever = Low
| | | | | Tuberculosis = Low
| | | | | Dispepsia = Low: Middle {Middle=1, High=0, Low=1}
| | | | | Skin Allergies = Middle: Middle {Middle=1, High=0, Low=0}
| | | | Influenza = Middle: Middle {Middle=2, High=0, Low=0}
| | | Common Cold = Middle: Middle {Middle=2, High=0, Low=0}
| Asthma = Middle
| | Gastritis = High: High {Middle=0, High=1, Low=0}
| | Gastritis = Middle: Middle {Middle=1, High=0, Low=0}
Diarrhea = Middle
| Influenza = Low: Low {Middle=0, High=0, Low=1}
| Influenza = Middle: High {Middle=0, High=1, Low=0}
    
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Figure 6. Classification rules for the spread of infectious diseases

The analytical model presented is also quite effective in presenting the up-to-date process of ML classification analysis. The update of the model can be seen based on the output of the analysis stages that have been carried out. The overall analysis results have been validated by measuring the level of accuracy and error as well as testing the performance and sensitivity of the analytical model. With these results, the proposed analytical model is able to provide an update on the previous model in describing the classification of the status of the spread of infectious diseases.

4. CONCLUSION

The development of classification analysis using ML gives quite good results. Overall, this study presents an updated analysis model for the classification of the status of the spread of infectious diseases. The analysis process provides output in two directions, namely classification based on data on the number of infected cases and population distribution. These results are obtained through pre-processing in order to obtain a precise and accurate analysis pattern. Classification analysis provides an accuracy rate of 99.77% and an error rate of 0.33%. Furthermore, the output of the classification results is also able to describe the DT with an accuracy of 91.67%. The DT will be used as an information and new knowledge for related parties. The knowledge gained can also be useful in carrying out environmental and community health management processes.

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